

Building translational scientists through cross-continent training and educational activities from classroom to commercialisation

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Introduction

Translating discoveries from laboratories into clinical practice that can help patients is a challenging process. Researchers excel in research discoveries and early-stage translation and often face translational roadblocks on the journey from preclinical studies to commercialisation. This highlights the need for training programs that can help translational researchers enhance their multidisciplinary skills, confidence, and ability to undertake various research-related tasks such as developing study design, data collection and analysis, and synthesis and reporting of research findings.

In 2019 members of [Translation Together \(TT\)](#), an international collaborative effort to advance translational innovation published a manuscript describing a global vision of seven fundamental characteristics of a translational scientist¹ ([The Fundamental Characteristics of a Translational Scientist](#)). Since the release of this paper, five TT partners (adMare BioInnovations, EATRIS, LifeArc, NCATS, Therapeutic Innovation Australia) have developed new or modified education and training initiatives to enhance the translational research workforce. In this paper, each TT organisation describes example(s) of operationalising the fundamental characteristics of a translational scientist in education activities.

The resulting training and educational activities produced vary in target audience, major focus and availability of opportunities. These are all based on “local” (ie country / geographical area specific) needs, but often the content developed and the methods employed can be translated across geographical and topic boundaries. All programs have faced, and continue to face, challenges in the initial set up and delivery of their programs, along with scalability and sustainability considerations to ensure the programs can deliver their intended impact. Measuring the impact of these programs raises additional challenges, but as many are still in their infancy, the full extent of their impact is difficult to calculate. As the organisations listed here work together within the TT collaboration it is hoped that through the sharing of best practices, educational / training materials and lessons learned, the programs can continue to develop and produce greater impacts.

Overview of programs

The organisations within TT have a number of ways in which they support the development of innovative therapeutics and practices, but each organisation was asked to highlight their major program(s) for supporting the professional development of researchers, in line with the “7 Characteristics” paper highlighted above. The programs focus on a range of career stages / levels and in the depth and length of learning opportunities provided, but each is complementary across the TT partnership. Some programs have been running for a number of years, but have been revised and reviewed under a new lens thanks to the 7 characteristics; whilst others have been developed and launched in the past 2-4 years with the 7 characteristics in mind. Table 1 provides a brief

comparison of the programs, focusing on the nature of the organisation in charge and funding source; target audience; delivery format and brief summary of the program (not including content). The program types can be categorised in a number of ways, but for the purposes of this report we have subdivided into those which are immersive, hands-on programs and those which are shorter in duration and (though still practical in nature) focus on acquisition of key skills and knowledge, with the aim of enabling them to apply these outside of the classroom.

Table 1: Overview of translational scientist development programs across TT collaboration partners

Organisation & country	Funding source / distribution	Program highlight & target audience	Format	Program summary
<u>National center for advancing translational Sciences</u> (NCATS), USA	Federally funded department of the US National Institutes of Health (NIH) organisation.	Translational science interagency fellowship – postdoctoral researchers	3 year research program with mentoring across agencies.	3 year research project with fellows time divided between NIH/NCATS & FDA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Postdoctoral researchers working on projects focused on innovation in pre-clinical research combined with training / mentoring in how such innovations can form part of the FDA regulatory review framework - Joint projects defined by NCATS & FDA scientists prior to recruitment, with fellows jointly mentored by scientists from both agencies - Projects based on pre-defined translational science priority areas for both agencies
<u>LifeArc</u> UK	Medical research charity, self-funded; facilities all under LifeArc umbrella.	Undergraduate research experience (URE) - undergraduate students 2 years into course Technology transfer fellows (TTF) program – early career professionals with a postgraduate degree;	Both programs are 12 month in-person placements	URE program Program in which students are employed on a fixed term contract to develop their experimental skills whilst building translational knowledge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Join a research team, performing a research role alongside other team members - Structured learning (lecture series) on drug development process Opportunities to explore other scientific roles eg Tech transfer TTF program Program designed to provide hands-on practical experience in tech transfer environments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 months spent at each of 4 collaborating centres - Live experience in each setting of managing tech transfer cases across a range of scientific areas
<u>Therapeutic Innovation Australia</u> (TIA), Australia	Government funded through National Collaborative Research Infrastructure	Pipeline accelerator voucher scheme – researchers at all levels who require access	In-person research opportunities and mentoring support.	A competitive voucher-style researcher access scheme providing subsidised access to TIA supported facilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables access to research infrastructure for scientists working on therapeutic development projects - Supports early career researchers to develop a track record in translational research - Provides guidance and support for next steps in the translational process from R&D to clinical development pathways

	e Strategy; distributed services across Australia.	to research capability and translational support		
<p><u>EATRIS</u> - <u>ERIC</u>, Europe (HQ in the Netherlands)</p>	<p>European research infrastructure, non-profit organisation; distributed services across Europe at affiliated institutes.</p>	<p>TMEX live course & e-learning – early career scientists Translational skills needs analysis in focused projects – review and support translational skills awareness and development across diverse project roles</p>	<p>Mixture of live training and online learning opportunities</p>	<p>TMEX & e-learning Providing introductory knowledge of the drug development process and the landscape of translational medicine</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixture of lectures and discussions in live courses - Online learning through videos and text-based tutorials <p>Translational skills needs analysis Raising awareness and highlighting key learning resources to those outside the translational research community.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing a view of translational research skills needs within projects focused on specific scientific areas eg By-COVID. - Bringing the translational elements into projects more focused on technology and basic research – ensuring researchers / infrastructure developers are aware of the needs and requirements for translation to take place - Aims to link in additional supporting resources which researchers can explore in more detail e.g. Innovation management toolbox
<p>adMare bioinnovations, Canada</p>	<p>Not for profit company; based across three founding institutes all under adMare umbrella.</p>	<p>BioInnovation Scientist program (BIS) - early career scientists in academia, or newly graduated scientists entering industry roles</p>	<p>Online learning, synchronous course with live interactive sessions</p>	<p>An 8 week cohort based program with 3 live webinars, approx. 25-30 hours for completion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed to broaden knowledge of therapeutics development and commercialisation - Initially built upon existing curated material with additional activities for critical thinking - Revised versions include EDI and accessibility issues in therapeutics and further opportunities for problem solving and critical thinking skills. <p>Live sessions allow for networking and communication skills development</p>

Immersive programs

Four of the organisations highlighted immersive programs, where scientists are fully involved in a hands-on “project” to gain the skills and knowledge required to become a fully-fledged translational researcher. The program with the longest duration is also the newest, the Translational science interagency fellowship (TSIF) organised by **NCATS** (a department of the US National Institutes of Health (NIH)). It is a 3-year postdoctoral training program run in collaboration with the U.S. Food & Drug Administration (FDA). The purpose of the fellowship is to create a training experience where fellows have projects that seamlessly integrate developing innovations in preclinical research (e.g., spanning informatics-related projects to developing more predictive models for assessing safety and efficacy of drugs to developing new therapies for rare diseases) with an understanding of the information required by the FDA to incorporate these innovations into a regulatory review framework. The dual project development and mentoring approach means projects can focus on topics of mutual interest and high priority to both agencies, with each project incorporating regulatory review considerations from the beginning. This streamlines the research that needs to be conducted and reduces potential roadblocks the project may experience in later stages of the translational process. TSIF fellows divide their time between NIH/NCATS and the FDA based on the needs of each individual project.

Of note, the program began after successfully receiving internal funding through NCATS' Operations Planning Committee. This funding secured the ability to recruit two postdoctoral fellows each year through to 2028 and support them for 3 years. The first cohort was onboarded in Sept. 2021 and projects are in progress (therefore it is too early to measure impact). Finding projects of mutual interest between NCATS and FDA has been a challenge, navigating potential translational barriers whilst also advancing the field. It required definition of agreed priority areas between both agencies coupled with advance planning and clear communication between FDA and NCATS mentors to achieve success.

LifeArc has the longest running program. Their undergraduate research experience program has been running since 2011 and is targeted at researchers at a much earlier point in their career. The program embeds students in research teams at LifeArc, providing them with a 1 year salaried position, normally between the 2nd and 3rd years of their undergraduate degree. During this immersion year, they gain a full set of experimental skills which enables them to place themselves ahead of many graduates when they enter the job market after completing their degrees. Alongside the research skills they are building in their daily work, students are also given formal learning on the drug discovery process as a whole, delivered by practicing industry scientists from within the organisation. Additionally, they are provided with opportunities to explore other scientific roles within the translational research ecosystem through shadowing, e.g. in technology transfer or communication roles. It is not only the students who gain from this experience however, as the supervisors are often early career scientists themselves, who also gain from taking on a supervisory and mentoring role.

LifeArc also provides an immersive experience, for a more focused group – the technology transfer fellows program. This newer program (running since 2019) enables those who wish to follow a career in tech transfer to gain a thorough knowledge and hands-on skillset in the subject, through a year-long program where fellows rotate around 4 tech transfer centres (these include LifeArc and three London Universities). Designed to address the shortfall in both number and skills of aspiring technology transfer professionals, these fellowships provide opportunities for individuals to test their aptitude for describing complex scientific information in accessible terms, ability to quickly grasp new scientific concepts and develop their written and oral communication skills – all key skills for success in these roles. The rotation across four participating sites enables fellows to gain

experience in a variety of activities across scientific and technology topics and different tech transfer practices. These again run for a full calendar year, fully immersing fellows in the environment in which they would practice if they enter these roles as a career.

The final immersive program is that highlighted by **TIA**, but their **Pipeline Accelerator voucher scheme** provides a different approach to key skill development. As a distributed research infrastructure, the TIA supports access to research facilities across Australia to further the translation of research findings into clinical application. Through a voucher scheme they enable researchers to access these resources, providing them with the opportunity to push their research forward in terms of experimental work. As a part of this process, they also receive mentoring and support in the development of their experimental questions and in the translational pathway they may follow. This targeted approach and guidance on the translational steps is key to their individual project success, as there is no one-size-fits-all approach in translational research. Additional learning opportunities arise through another voucher scheme called the **Technical Feasibility Assessments (TFAs)**, where researchers have the opportunity to work through their project plans in a workshop like environment with experts at the translational facilities, culminating in the provision of a report with personalised recommendations. Not only do the researchers gain the much-needed direction for initiating translational research, but the workshop environment also enables them to build knowledge of the process and requirements involved and improve their early-stage decision making skills.

Short course formats

In 2016 EATRIS ran their first iteration of the **Translational Medicine Explained course (TMEX)** under funding from the C-COMEND project. Developed to provide an overview of the Translational medicine and drug development process, it has developed into an annually run course funded through grants (most recently from the La Caixa Foundation). The course was developed as a one-week face to face (f2f) event, providing a mix of theoretical and hands-on sessions, along with opportunities for formal and informal discussion, encouraging networking between participants and speakers.

The course was reviewed in the light of the 7 characteristics publication, and these characteristics now serve as the start point for all courses. The content has developed further and has been adjusted since the first edition. One of the challenges is in covering the broad range of topics forming translational research in a one-week duration. Speakers on the course are from both academic and industrial backgrounds when possible sourced locally from the organising host institution, eg when held at Bayer in 2023, a number of the key speakers were experts from Bayer itself. Uniquely, the patient voice is always included in TMEX courses, through the inclusion of patient representatives as speakers, and through having participants from patient organisations. The typical audience is 2nd year PhD students upwards, mainly from an academic setting, but the course is also open to those in industry and more senior scientists wishing to expand their knowledge. Though a short course in duration, the environment is immersive for the week, with a full program on each day.

The f2f course is also supported by online materials, which participants are requested to work through as a pre-requisite for the live course. These materials are also made available through an online portal, the **Transmed academy**, enabling anyone with an interest in learning more about translational research to work through the course in an asynchronous manner. Additional courses in related translational topics are also available through this portal, again available in a free and open manner.

Another focus for EATRIS has been in developing awareness and basic knowledge of translational research principles, especially in the areas of regulatory requirements and innovation management, for researchers and infrastructure developers unfamiliar with Translational Research. Raising awareness of translational skills, especially those that relate to the 7 characteristics, supports efforts in ensuring that basic research outputs are translated into patient benefit as part of large-scale multidisciplinary projects. Exposing researchers to introductory online materials such as available through Transmed academy or to resources such as the Innovation Management Toolbox, a self-service web-based library providing guidance on R&D primarily for Rare Diseases, expands the pool of researchers who are aware of translational matters. A major challenge, however remains in ensuring that materials are findable by those outside of the translational community, with FAIRification² of training (events and materials) being a major driver here.

The Bioinnovation scientist program (BIS) developed by **adMare Bioinnovations** in Canada was created following a 2019 study of skills needs, focused on enabling the growth of the Canadian life sciences industry. This study involved over 30 Canadian industry leaders, along with international experts, opinion leaders in the life sciences and extensive reviews of talent development programs and in-house training from Canada and beyond. Recognising that the skills which enable academic scientists to be successful do not necessarily translate across to industry success, the transition between the two is challenging for many, especially as the therapeutics development processes are not widely exposed in academia. The Canadian life science industry is predominantly composed of small and medium sized biopharma companies who are generally not in a position to provide formal development programs to help support these transitions.

The BIS program was therefore developed to enable early-career scientists to develop skills needed to succeed in industry, by broadening their knowledge of therapeutics development and commercialization, and by building their professional skills and networks. The program was initially built through the curation of relevant existing courses with the addition of questions and discussion points to encourage deeper thinking and engagement amongst participants. It was developed to run online in an asynchronous manner with a continual enrolment process, targeting scientists who were at post-graduate level in academic settings, or new graduates seeking employment / having recently been employed in industry.

The program has since been re-designed to a cohort-based model, for a study period of 8 weeks. Whilst still run online, the program includes live webinars (to increase inter participant engagement) and new content including EDI and accessibility issues, along with more opportunities for developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. At the same time the amount of time required to work through the course has been reduced, increasing the completion rate greatly and improving the overall feedback.

Meeting the 7 characteristics

The programs described through this report so far have all focused on developing the 7 characteristics of a translational scientist. However, the way in which the 7 characteristics have been implemented does differ between each program, with some variation coming from local requirements (i.e. focusing on topics which are of greater need in those organisations / geographical areas), or by the capacity of the organisation (either through human or economic resource) to deliver programs at an appropriate scale.

The characteristics described are complex skills to develop, and are not necessarily easy to approach in a one size fits all curriculum – but a variety of training propositions and of training material

allowing for further development across the organisations within the TT collaboration and into other organisations who wish to expand their translational training offering.

It is interesting to review some key examples of how each of the 7 characteristics can be developed from across the programs described above, see table 2 below.

Table 2: Highlighted examples of characteristic development through the programs

Characteristic	Program highlights
Boundary crosser	LifeArc Tech transfer fellow: Successful translation from a tech transfer point of view needs individuals who can work collaboratively (and encourage collaboration) across disciplines, from a number of research areas through to financial and legal topics. Through their fellowships, LifeArc fellow have opportunities to interact and build their experience in a number of different tech transfer methods, enabling them to develop their approach to the boundary crossing required.
Domain expert	All programs: all programs described start at the level of domain expertise, whether at undergraduate level or above. All programs build upon a foundation of life / medical sciences and expand knowledge into the translational space from this start point.
Team player	LifeArc URE: undergraduates who join LifeArc for their year long placement are immediately part of a research team and learn the importance of team science from the outset. Through formal learning and shadowing they also gain experience of the different roles in successfully translating research into application.
Process innovator	NCATS interagency fellowship: these fellowships are directly focused on looking at innovative practices for translation, whilst also being able to look at the regulatory impact and needs to ensure the innovation is not stifled by regulatory requirements.
Skilled communicator	EATRIS TMEX: By ensuring that the patient voice is always part of the f2f course, alongside industry and academic voices, participants gain knowledge of the power of communicating across all audiences involved in research and the importance of the community voice. They also have opportunities to practice their communication through elevator pitches of their work and both informal and formal discussions with all participants.
Systems thinker	AdMare Bioinnovation BIS: introduces learners to the world of therapeutics discovery, development, and commercialisation, allowing learners to evaluate the complexity of bringing research discoveries to market.
Rigorous researcher	TIA Pipeline accelerator: providing researchers with support and guidance to work through a specific element of their research at a translational facility whilst also guiding them through the next steps in the process. By working with domain and translational experts they ensure their research is undertaken in a robust manner and will yield results which can be applied in the next steps of the translational process

A major component of all programs is discussion and problem solving, often encouraged in a team scenario. Translational scientists do not work alone, and this ability to discuss ideas with others (especially from a diverse set of backgrounds) is fundamental to ensuring the translational process runs smoothly. What has not been discussed is the level of competence required in all these characteristics? Should all individuals be expected to be fully competent in all skill sets? It is unlikely that this would be the case and may be dependent on the exact role individuals take in the process of translation. Whilst it may be easy to teach many of the characteristics (or ways to develop them) there is still an individual learning and development process that needs to take place; and this may take time outside of the original teaching / learning opportunity.

Moving ahead – scalability, sustainability and impact

The impact of these programs is still under review, and for some (eg TSIF), it is too early to draw results at this stage. There is clear interest from individuals wishing to enter these programs, with all those reviewed demonstrating a continued interest through recruitment numbers; with destination details available for a number of the “older” immersive programs and completion rates for shorter courses.

There are a number of challenges in building skills associated with the translational process and specifically with the 7 characteristics of a Translational Scientist as described in 2019. A major obstacle is the recognition that the translation process itself is complex, and not a discipline that is routinely taught alongside other research practices as a standard part of higher education programs. Often it forms part of an added learning opportunity during postgraduate study (eg TMEX), as a step in a research career pathway (eg TSIF), or as part of a research pipeline (eg TIA’s pipeline accelerator).

Scalability and sustainability continue to be additional challenges. More immersive programs provide a depth of learning over a timescale which allows trainees the opportunity to broaden their understanding of the Translational Research processes in a guided / supported manner, but which require significant expert time in mentoring and supervision, along with the funding requirement to support learners for the length of the program. Due to the close supervisory nature of such programs, they are often limited in the number of seats available – they do not scale easily as this would require significant numbers of supervisors, potentially reducing their ability to undertake their actual job. For the shorter courses, scalability is potentially less of an issue as experts are required for shorter periods of time and if a pool of experts is available, the teaching load can be more evenly spread. Financial constraints remain; either for the learning organisation due to the costs of delivering such a course, or for the participants, when participating in such training programs is not directly linked to research progress. Additional educational materials are often produced alongside training programs that can further support professional development and potentially enlarge the pool of trainees eg TIA guidance documents and EATRIS developed toolboxes, however those self-service resources suffer from a lack of visibility. More needs to be done to allow findability of both, educational programs and complementary resources.

Conclusion

The report presented here has described the approaches of five members of the Translation Together collaboration in providing education and training opportunities to support (mainly) life science researchers in developing the 7 fundamental characteristics of a translational scientist. The programs introduced demonstrate the variety of methods employed to develop these characteristics, which whilst run in separate instances, can all be seen as complementary activities. There is a need to continue working within the collaboration to share best practices, experiences and content / materials developed across all partners, to further develop existing programs to meet their full potential. There is also the potential to encourage and engage organisations outside of the current collaboration to share and learn from the knowledge and experiences described here, so that further programs may be developed and delivered for maximising output of translational research and ensure the next generation of scientists is well equipped to become translational researchers.

References

- 1 The fundamental characteristics of a translational scientist. C. Taylor Gilliland *et al*; *ACS Pharmacol. Transl. Sci.* 2019, 2, 3, 213–216
- 2 Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. L. Garcia *et al*; *PLOS Computational Biology* 16(5): e1007854.

Links

Translation together (TT): <https://translationtogether.org/>

National center for advancing translational sciences (NCATS): <https://ncats.nih.gov/>

LifeArc: <https://www.lifearc.org/about/>

Therapeutic innovation Australia (TIA): <https://therapeuticinnovation.com.au/>

EATRIS-ERIC (EATRIS): <https://eatris.eu/>

AdMare Bioinnovations: <https://www.admarebio.com/en/>

NCATS fellowship: <https://ncats.nih.gov/research/training-education/training-at-ncats/TSIF>

LifeArc research experience: <https://www.lifearc.org/careers/students-and-fellows/work-experience-and-placements-3/>

LifeArc technology transfer fellowship: <https://www.lifearc.org/careers/students-and-fellows/fellowships/technology-transfer-fellowships-2/>

TIA Pipeline accelerator voucher scheme: <https://therapeuticinnovation.com.au/pipeline-accelerator/>

EATRIS TMEX: <https://eatris.eu/events/tmex-translational-medicine-explained-5-day-winter-school-2023/>

EATRIS Transmed academy: <https://eatris.eu/transmed-academy/>

AdMare BIS program: <https://www.admarebio.com/en/talent>